

SUSTAINABLE STRATEGIES IN ONLINE FOOD DELIVERY BY FOOD ESTABLISHMENTS IN DUMAGUETE CITY

Helen Torres Cabije

Lyceum of the Philippines University – Manila, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12740090>

ABSTRACT

Online food delivery is when you order food from a restaurant through the internet or a mobile app, and the restaurant delivers it to your doorstep. This study measures the sustainable strategies of food establishments utilizing online food deliveries in Dumaguete City using a descriptive-correlational design. Thirty food establishments in Dumaguete City served as the respondents of this research. The study examines sustainable strategies in Dumaguete City's food establishments, finding consensus among respondents on employment, safety, service accessibility, responsiveness, and environmental aspects. Challenges in food delivery services were acknowledged, prompting a need for sustainable strategies to guide managerial decisions. Significant correlations emerged between demographic profiles and sustainable practices, notably, operational tenure impacting employment dynamics, and gender/education influencing customer relations. Technology facilitated efficient order processing, particularly evident in establishments with well-educated owners. Interestingly, respondents' profiles did not affect pandemic-related challenges, highlighting the universality of sustainable strategies' importance. The study concludes a significant relationship between challenges and sustainable practices, emphasizing the role of a conducive work environment in mitigating hurdles. Advanced technology, notably online food delivery services, fosters innovation, and operational efficiency, underscoring its significance in enhancing food service establishments' performance.

Keywords: *Online Food Delivery, Sustainable Strategies, Restaurants, Correlational Research, Dumaguete City*

INTRODUCTION

The Online Food Delivery (OFD) service industry has emerged as a new wave in the food and beverage industry. The rise of the OFD industry has provided job opportunities for many people across a range of types of employment including chefs and administrative staff in restaurants, delivery people, or programmers behind the application/online platforms (Li, Miroso, & Bremer, 2020). Owners and managers of the food service industry are continuously engaged in the use of OFD to minimize costs and increase profit (Kapoor & Vij, 2018). Customers no longer have to repeat delivery address, food order, fees, etc. to the phone operator after ordering via text message or e-mail. Eventually, the food delivery system transitioned to a mobile platform thereby providing patrons with an additional level of convenience. OFD strategically upgraded the apps making them more user-friendly and interactive. Because of numerous technological breakthroughs and globalization, e-commerce is geared towards virtual diversion. OFD's apps cater to almost all the demands of the market segmentation to achieve an enormous return on investment.

The Philippines is one of the countries that heavily utilize OFD services. OFD service apps provide almost everything that customer's need in regard to buying food and beverages. Utilizing these apps, customers can look up all nearby restaurants, see the menu options, and select the food or beverages of choice (Kapoor & Vij, 2018). Furthermore, food service industry enrolled in OFDS apps because it is equipped with digital payment instruments that are more convenient, and attractive at the same time increase brand awareness (Chai, &Yat, 2019). Other factors, including ease of use, navigational design, and performance expectancy, influence customer satisfaction (Prasetyo et. al, 2021, Chai &Yat, 2019, Yeo, Goh & Rezaei, 2017). In this new set-up many are still in the process of adjustment, soon enough customers will become accustomed to these new apps, and they can eliminate technical issues and difficulties due to familiarity. This is a gap that can be considered in the study. Even though technical issues are decreasing, it is not sufficient enough to solely observe technology acceptance factors. According to Statista (2018), our country's online food delivery market is worth around P11 billion, with nearly eight million Filipinos using the service at least once. With such a large number of customers, many people are enticed to open online food stores from the convenience of their own homes. Owing to high demand and customers' preference to eat meals off-premise, complexities of food production and delivery logistics become apparent.

The COVID-19 pandemic greatly influenced the increased demand for online food delivery of restaurants in Dumaguete enrolled in OFD Service Apps. The convenience and time-saving factors are key elements of these developments (*interbrandspackaging.com*). Food delivery services in Dumaguete have drastically changed, consumers order food online rather than going to a restaurant. The observable gap that the researchers will address is how OFDS be able to have sustainable strategies. This study aims to determine the sustainable strategies in online food delivery by food establishments in Dumaguete City.

Research Questions

This research intends to determine the sustainable strategies in online food delivery by food establishments in Dumaguete City. Furthermore, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the socio-demographic profile of the respondents and organizational profile of the food establishments?
2. What are the sustainable strategies of the food establishments in utilizing food delivery services in Dumaguete City?
3. What are the common challenges encountered by food establishments in utilizing food delivery services?
4. Is the socio-demographic and organizational profile of the respondents relevant to the sustainable strategies and challenges encountered by the food establishments using food delivery services?
5. Are the sustainable strategies of the food establishments using food delivery services in Dumaguete City relevant to the challenges they encounter?

METHODOLOGY

This research used a correlational design. As described, correlational research is used to determine prevalence and relationships among variables and to forecast events from current data and knowledge. The use of this design for the study is justified by the research's aim which was to determine the degree of relationships between the socio-demographic and organizational profile of the respondents to the sustainable strategies and challenges encountered by the food establishments using food delivery services, and the relationship between the sustainable strategies of the food establishments using food delivery services and challenges they encountered. The whole purpose of using the correlational method was to figure out which variables were related and to develop prediction models for the value of a variable. Correlational studies are carried out either to help explain important human behaviors or to predict likely outcomes. If a relationship of sufficient magnitude exists between two variables, it becomes possible to predict a score on one variable if a score on the other variable is known.

The respondents of the study are the owners and/or managers of food establishments utilizing FoodPanda and GrabFood food delivery services. The research was focused on identifying opportunities and challenges in the food delivery industry. The study also looks at the demographic composition of the industry. The survey only includes food business owners/managers utilizing food delivery services. Purposive sampling was used in the study to select who among the individuals of the population fit all the criteria and could participate in the study to reach the number of respondents needed to participate in the study. Purposive sampling is a sampling approach in which the researcher chooses members of the population to participate in the study based on the researchers' judgment or criteria. A total of Thirty (30) food establishments that are utilizing the FoodPanda and GrabFood delivery services were selected purposively and

the one to answer the survey questionnaire can either be the owner or the manager of the above-mentioned establishment.

The main instrument for the data gathering was a survey questionnaire divided into three parts. Part I focuses on the personal and institutional profiles. Part II focuses on the sustainable strategies of the restaurants in terms of employment, safety, accessibility of the service, responsiveness, and environment. Part III shows the challenges encountered by the food establishments using delivery services. In line with the aim of the study to determine sustainable strategies for restaurants amidst the pandemic through food delivery in Dumaguete City, the study correlate between the socio-demographic profile of the respondents to the sustainable strategies and challenges encountered by the restaurants using food delivery services, and the relationship between the sustainable strategies of the food establishments using food delivery services and challenges they encountered.

RESULTS

Respondents' Personal Profile and Institutional Profile

Table 1 shows the socio-demographic profile of the respondents and the institutional profile of the food establishments in Dumaguete City.

Table 1. Socio-demographic and organizational profile.

Variables	f	%
Age Bracket		
51- 70	2	6.67
41- 50	2	6.67
31- 40	13	43.33
26- 30	10	33.33
20- 25	3	10.00
Sex		
Male	13	43.33
Female	17	56.66
Marital Status		
Married	7	23.33
Single	23	76.67
Educational Attainment		
College Graduate	24	80.00
College Undergraduate	6	20.00
Type of Food Establishment		
Bistro	9	30.00
Restaurant	17	56.67

Fast Food	2	6.67
Cake House	2	6.67
Type of Ownership		
Sole Proprietorship	12	40.00
Corporation	11	36.67
Partnership	7	23.33
Number of Employees		
17 - 20 regulars	3	10
13 - 16 regulars	4	13.34
9 - 12 regulars	10	33.33
5 - 8 regulars	7	23.33
1- 4 regulars	6	20
Number of Years in Business Operation		
30.01 years – 40 years and above	3	10.00
20.01 years – 30 years	2	6.67
10.01 years- 20 years	3	10.00
5.01 years – 10 years	6	20.00
3.01 years – 5 years	3	10.00
1.01 years- 3 years	6	20.00
1 month – 1 year	7	23.33

N=30

Sustainable Strategies of Food Delivery Services

The sustainable strategies of food delivery services of the food establishments in Dumaguete City can help assess the current situation to proactively address the issues and discover opportunities for improvements.

Table 2 shows the extent of the sustainable strategies of food delivery services of the food establishments in Dumaguete City.

Table 2. Sustainable strategies of food delivery services

Variables	WX	Verbal Description
Employment	3.68	Strongly Agree
1. Additional employment in the city	3.73	Strongly Agree
2. Increase job opportunities/ help create more jobs	3.73	Strongly Agree
3. More business opportunities	3.60	Strongly Agree
4. Gives better pay to the delivery driver	3.67	Strongly Agree
Safety	3.51	Strongly Agree

1. No misunderstandings and no frustrations	3.23	Agree
2. Safer and healthier for customers and businesses	3.67	Strongly Agree
3. Less risk/exposure to get infected of any disease	3.53	Strongly Agree
4. Minimal contact between servers and customers	3.60	Strongly Agree
Accessibility of the Service	3.61	Strongly Agree
1. An improved customer experience	3.67	Strongly Agree
2. Easy to access and cost efficiency	3.53	Strongly Agree
3. Less hassle for the customers	3.77	Strongly Agree
4. Customers have better choices	3.47	Strongly Agree
Responsiveness	3.56	Strongly Agree
1. Quick and convenient delivery	3.57	Strongly Agree
2. A seamless process and less room for error	3.33	Strongly Agree
3. It's just one click away using a mobile device / You can receive an order for a takeaway by phone	3.70	Strongly Agree
4. It's fast, easy, and comfortable	3.63	Strongly Agree
Work Environment	3.72	Strongly Agree
1. Increases the number of customers you can service	3.73	Strongly Agree
2. Make up for reduced foot traffic	3.73	Strongly Agree
3. Increase your visibility and reach in your area and add an extra stream of income	3.77	Strongly Agree
4. Streamlined restaurant operations	3.63	Strongly Agree

Legend: Range of Values Verbal Description

3.25- 4.00	Strongly Agree (SA)
2.50- 3.24	Agree (A)
1.75- 2.49	Disagree (D)
1.00- 1.74	Strongly Disagree (SD)

Challenges in The Food Delivery Services

The challenges in the food delivery services of the food establishments in Dumaguete City aid in gaining a better understanding of the issues faced by food establishments while using food delivery services.

Table 3. Challenges in the Food Delivery Services

Indicators	WX	Verbal Description
1. Shifting Customer preferences	3.23	Agree
2. Unstable Market Prices	3.17	Agree
3. Adhering to the Food Quality Standards	3.43	Strongly Agree
4. Managing Customer Expectations	3.43	Strongly Agree
5. Improper Food Handling	2.43	Disagree

6. Threat of Bigger Players	3.00	Agree
7. The Logistics Dilemma	2.47	Disagree
8. Traffic Situation	3.10	Agree
10. Fake Booking	2.33	Disagree
11. Weather Condition	3.20	Agree
Composite Mean		2.71 Agree

Legend:

Range of Values	Verbal Description
3.25- 4.00	Strongly Agree (SA)
2.50- 3.24	Agree (A)
1.75- 2.49	Disagree (D)
1.00- 1.74	Strongly Disagree (SD)

Test of Significant Relationship

Significant Relationship between the profile and the sustainable strategies of food delivery services. This data is significant in understanding how the profile of the respondents corresponds to their perception of the sustainable strategies on the food delivery strategies.

Table 4. Test of Significant Relationship Between the Profile and the Sustainable Strategies of Food Delivery Services

Variables		Age	Sex	Civil Status	Highest Educ. Attainment	Type of Food Establishment	Type of Owner	Size of Org.	Years of Operation
Employment	Correlation	-.043	.251	.198	.077	.200	.037	-.236	-.356*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.822	.180	.293	.687	.289	.847	.208	.050
	Remarks	Not Sig.	Not Sig.	Not Sig.	Not Sig.	Not Sig.	Not Sig.	Not Sig.	Significant
Safety	Correlation	-.022	.366*	.167	.358*	-.011	-.182	-.298	.059
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.907	.047	.378	.050	.955	.337	.110	.758
	Remarks	Not Sig.	Significant	Not Sig.	Significant	Not Sig.	Not Sig.	Not Sig.	Not Sig.
Accessibility of the service	Correlation	-.030	.137	.010	.233	.157	-.135	-.141	-.104
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.875	.471	.959	.216	.406	.478	.458	.585
	Remarks	Not Sig.	Not Sig.	Not Sig.	Not Sig.	Not Sig.	Not Sig.	Not Sig.	Not Sig.

Responsiveness	Correlation	.070	.408*	.138	.496**	.153	-.119	-.244	-.070
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.711	.025	.469	.005	.420	.531	.194	.714
	Remarks	Not Sig.	Significant	Not Sig.	Significant	Not Sig.	Not Sig.	Not Sig.	Not Sig.
Environment	Correlation	.164	.348	-.030	.448*	.362*	-.223	-.245	-.041
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.386	.060	.874	.013	.049	.237	.191	.829
	Remarks	Not Sig.	Not Sig.	Not Sig.	Significant	Significant	Not Sig.	Not Sig.	Not Sig.

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed), $p \leq .05$

Test of Significant Relationship Between the Profile and the Challenges

Table 5 presents the test of the significant relationship between the profile and the challenges. Data presented here will show the correlation of the respondent's profile to the challenges encountered with the food delivery services. This information will enable the researcher to verify whether the profile plays a significant role in identifying the challenges.

Table 5. Test of Significant Relationship between the Profile and the Challenges

Variables		Challenges	
Spearman's rho	Age	Correlation	.210
		Coefficient	
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.266
		Remarks	Not Significant
Sex		Correlation	.174
		Coefficient	
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.357
		Remarks	Not Significant
Status		Correlation	-.151
		Coefficient	
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.426
		Remarks	Not Significant
Highest Educational Attainment		Correlation	.131
		Coefficient	
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.492
		Remarks	Not Significant
Type Food Establishment		Correlation	-.011
		Coefficient	
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.952
		Remarks	Not Significant

Type Ownership	Correlation	-.029
	Coefficient	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.879
Remarks		Not Significant
Size Organization	Correlation	.166
	Coefficient	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.381
Remarks		Not Significant
Years Operation	Correlation	.052
	Coefficient	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.784
Remarks		Not Significant

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed), $p \leq .05$

Test of Significant Relationship between the Challenges and the Sustainable Strategies of Food Delivery Services

The test of the significant relationship between the challenges and the sustainable strategies of food delivery services will help the proponent determine how the identified challenges relate to the sustainable strategies that are currently implemented by the food delivery services.

Table 6 Test of Significant Relationship between the Challenges and the Sustainable Strategies of Food Delivery Services

Variables		Challenges
Employment	Pearson Correlation	.019
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.923
	Remarks	Not Significant
Safety	Pearson Correlation	-.204
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.279
	Remarks	Not Significant
Accessibility	Pearson Correlation	-.129
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.497
	Remarks	Not Significant
Responsiveness	Pearson Correlation	-.081
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.670
	Remarks	Not Significant
Environment	Pearson Correlation	.352*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.05
	Remarks	Significant

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed), $p \leq .05$

DISCUSSION

For the socio-demographic profile of the respondents, the results indicate that many of the respondents are between the ages of 31 and 40. It means that the respondents are capable of managing or owning a firm. According to the study of Azoulay et. al (2020) the average age for establishing a business is in the late 30s or early 40s. Age does predict success, and it predicts it dramatically, but not in the sense that many believe. It shows the same result as in this undertaking; most of the owner and/or managers of restaurants in Dumaguete City are between the ages of 30 to 40 years old.

In terms of sex, most of the respondents were female. Most of restaurant owners or managers were female, as they were often in charge of running establishments that were known for having great management in terms of cleanliness and housekeeping. Housekeeping, meal preparation, sanitation, and other household duties were examples. Females were thought to have a natural affinity for these items and were excellent at engaging customers. The presence of women in the industry is making the provision of services more complex because of their passive nature where they can address the caring needs of the customers (Asinas et. al, 2019).

It also reveals that the majority of the respondents were single. As revealed in on the sex of the respondents, many of them are females, this means that F&B establishments managed by single women can work effectively (Tayco et.al, 2023). According to the study of Uike & Gupta (2019), single persons had a better 'attitude toward behavior' and a better 'perceived behavioral control' than married people. In addition, married persons had a higher 'subjective norm' than unmarried people, and were more focused on running their businesses.

For their educational attainment, the majority of the respondents were college graduates. According to Omri & Afi (2020) suggests that higher levels of education result in better performance in entrepreneurial activities. Individuals with a higher level of education may also have a higher probability of achieving success and achieving their personal goals. These respondents graduated in different courses yet they are in the food business which helps boost the hospitality industry in Dumaguete City.

As for the organizational profile, most of the food establishments were restaurants. Most of the food establishments were restaurants that were built or situated in the desired façade and interior design. A restaurant's physical atmosphere can make a strong first impression on entering customers. The physical and service surroundings had an impact on customer satisfaction during the eating experience. Additionally, every restaurant owner always wants to make his/her restaurant unique and appealing which depicts the owner's personality. According to the study of Ishak et. al (2020), the architectural design, interior design, and decorations that add to the attractiveness of the physical environment that draws the client in every way are referred to as facility aesthetics.

With regard to type of ownership, many of the food establishments were classified as sole proprietorship type of ownership. Sole proprietorships is one of the frequent types

of business ownership since they are straightforward to set up and operate. They are a good choice for someone who wants to try out a low-risk enterprise. According to Entrepreneur Asia Pacific, because of its simplicity, ease of setup, and low cost, the sole proprietorship was a popular business structure. One of the most appealing aspects of a sole proprietorship was its ease of formation. It is only necessary to buy and sell goods or services. To start a sole proprietorship, no formal filing or event is required; it is a status that evolves naturally through one's company activity.

Regarding the number of employees, many of the restaurants have 9-12 employees. The number of employees in an establishment depends on the size of the organization. The bigger the establishment, the more employees are needed or required. According to the study of Chaturvedi & Karri (2021), a firm's proportionate growth is independent of its absolute size. Several researchers, however, have contested this and have repeatedly asserted a contrary view, namely that the size and capacity of a firm have a significant impact on its performance.

Lastly, for the number of years in business operation, many of the food establishments operated for less than a year which means they are new in the business. New entries have even appeared in one category, "grab-and-go services," which includes food trucks and bakeries. These openings and reopenings have been sustained by focusing on health and safety, as well as new approaches to serve their customers, including moving their services and patrons outdoors (*qsrmagazine.com*).

For the sustainable strategies of food delivery services of the food establishments in Dumaguete City. The respondents agreed that the food establishments they are connected have sustainable strategies on employment, safety, accessibility of the service, responsiveness, and environment.

In terms of employment, respondents strongly agreed that food delivery services of the food establishments in Dumaguete City gives "additional employment in the city", and "increase job opportunities/ help create more jobs". This was true as the researcher can see that more food delivery drivers can be seen around the city after a few months when the pandemic started. According to Li, Miroso, and Bremer, (2020), the rise of the OFD industry has provided job opportunities for many people across a range of types of employment, including chefs and administrative staff at restaurants, delivery people, and programmers behind the apps/online platforms. Furthermore, the large OFD platforms employ thousands of individuals as delivery persons. The study of Muangmee et. al (2021), explains that there is no doubt that the OFD industry has created many jobs, particularly in the delivery sector.

For safety, respondents agreed that their safety strategies were sustainable. They observed that their FD services were "safer and healthier for customers and businesses", and there was "minimal contact between servers and customers". According to the study by Somashekhar et. al (2020), most restaurants have strict health and safety rules in place to safeguard both their employees and their customers, encompassing everything from sourcing to preparation and service. Food service companies have responded by

offering contactless pick-up options, which eliminate the need for customers to interact with personnel.

As for accessibility of the service, the respondents agreed on the service specified on the items; “less hassle for the customers”, and “an improved customer experience”. In the study of Hong et. al (2021), the advent of integrated OFD platforms, such as Food Panda and Grab Food, aided the expansion of OFD services. Customers who use OFD services enjoy a variety of perks, including not having to wait in line, not having to travel for pick-up, and not having to deal with order misunderstandings, which occur regularly in restaurants or when ordering over the phone, and discounts from daily deals.

With regards to responsiveness, respondents agreed that they have excellent strategies, especially on items: “it’s just one click away using a mobile device / you can receive an order for a takeaway by phone”, and it’s fast, easy, and comfortable. The traditional model of delivery where the customer contacts the restaurant, orders food, and then waits for the restaurant to deliver the food, has been the most popular type of delivery. The study of Kapoor & Vij (2018), explains the market is being redefined as a result of the advent of digital technologies. Customers use mobile apps or websites to locate all nearby restaurants, browse the menu, choose the cuisine they want to eat, and order the food with a single click or tap of a finger. When it comes to online food ordering, consumers who are used to shopping through apps or websites with maximum convenience and transparency expect the same experience.

Lastly, for the work environment, the respondents agreed that they have effective strategies. According to them it “increases their visibility and reach in their area and adds an extra stream of income”, “increases the number of customers they can provide service”, and “make up for reduced foot traffic. Indeed, food delivery is an additional income to the business because most people would prefer not to go out. Owners and managers have stated that the ultimate purpose or goal is to deliver food to their customers' doorstep and to limit the movement of the people. They appreciated the food delivery apps that enable anyone to place an order and have it delivered promptly and securely. Food delivery services have aided restaurants in reaching out to those who are unaware of their existence and are interested in the cuisines they offer. Li, Miroso, & Bremer (2020) study explained how the service works, once a purchase order is received, the platform sends a message to riders who match certain criteria, such as proximity to the platform and a favorable status. The service is assigned to the first person who responds. The meal is then picked up from the restaurant and delivered to the consumer within a certain amount of time (usually one hour). Naturally, the sooner the delivery is finished, the sooner the rider is free to accept new orders. While riders are compensated for each delivery, platforms charge a percentage of the meal order to the restaurant. The customer is additionally charged for delivery. Although the size, number of users, and geographic reach of these platforms are constantly growing, many questions remain.

For the challenges in the food delivery services, the respondents agreed on the challenges in food delivery services of the food establishments in Dumaguete City. Specifically, they agreed on items: “adhering to the food quality standards”, “managing

customer expectations”, “shifting customer preferences”, “unstable market prices”, “traffic situation”, “weather conditions”, and “threat of bigger players”. The business owners’ top challenges were adhering to the food quality standards and managing customer expectations. Well, this was very important especially when the business was providing customer service, and this will also give a good review to the business which attracts more customers. Food businesses will react quickly enough to this change in customer demand to avoid a decline in profitability. The study of Zhao & Bacao (2020), explains that customer happiness was linked to food quality and service efficiency, which had a substantial impact on the use of online meal delivery services. Meanwhile, they discovered that order conformity, delivery quality, meal quality, and pricing were the most important factors influencing whether or not people use online food delivery services.

However, respondents disagree on items: “logistics dilemma”, “improper food handling”, and “fake booking”. Since Dumaguete City is a developing city, challenges such as logistics and fake booking were not problems like what other big cities are experiencing. Improper food handling was also not a challenge for the business owner, because food establishment always gives their best services to have return customers. Dumaguete City is also known as the “City of Gentle People”, and is also dubbed as “the Center of Learning in the South”, providing the best services is already a priority for all businesses in the City. See-Kwong et al., (2017) explained that technology has played a significant role in transforming the food delivery service from phone-based to online ordering to meet customers' ever-changing demands and propel it to the top.

For the test of the significant relationship between the profile and the sustainable strategies of food delivery services. As shown in the table, employment is negatively correlated with years of operation with $r(30) = -.36, p = .05$ which means that the number of years in business operation can influence either an increase or decrease in the employment status. While sex $r(30) = .366, p = .047$, and highest educational attainment $r(30) = .358, p = .050$ are positively correlated to safety. This elucidates that sex and educational status can influence how business establishments implement business operations specifically in establishing a good relationship with the customers. More so the responsiveness when compared with sex and educational attainment were also positively correlated. This supports the idea that quickness in receiving orders and response to such requests are smoothly implemented using technology and these are achieved through constant training and updates with what is the latest in terms of technology that brought a change in the ways of living of the people/customers.

In terms of work environment t , it is evident that it can be influenced by the educational attainment $r(30) = .448, p = .013$ and type of establishment $r(30) = .632, p = .049$. This means that creating a good work environment in business can be determined when business owners have deeper educational background while such improvement or changes must be within the type of establishment or services being offered.

The socio-demographic profile of the respondents is relevant to the sustainable strategies. There is a significant relationship between sex and highest educational attainment in safety therefore the sex variables with the highest educational attainment

were well-informed about the safety of food establishment operations during the pandemic, which could be due to female managers and or owners of food establishments being exposed to the operation and their commitment to food safety. The work environment is also significant to the highest educational attainment; therefore, it signifies that with the highest educational attainment, the workplace relationships with the collaboration between the food establishments and the food delivery services and the efficiency and employee's health were apparent. According to Fu et. al (2019), owners of restaurants with a high level of education and formal training learned how to operate and manage a restaurant by working for others. Good business was the most significant aspect of this person's job happiness, and he believed that hard effort, honesty, and good customer service were the most important factors in a business's success.

On the test of the significant relationship between the profile and the challenges. All identified independent variables were not correlated with challenges. Age, $r(30) .210, p=.266$, Gender $r(30) .174, p=.357$, Status $r(30) -.151, p=.426$, Highest Educational Attainment $r(30) .131, p=.492$, Type of Food Establishment $r(30) -.011, p=.952$, Type of Ownership $r(30) -.029, p=.879$, Size of the Organization $r(30) .166, p=.381$, and Years in Business Operation, $r(30) .052, p=.784$.

The socio-demographic profile of the respondents was not relevant to the challenges encountered by the restaurants using food delivery services, therefore, there is no significant relationship between the respondent's profile and the challenges experienced by the business owners during this time of the pandemic. Thus, the null hypothesis of no relationship is accepted between the respondent's profile and the challenges in the food delivery services. According to Burhan et. al (2021), the hospitality industry was hit the hardest, as worldwide and local travel fell as a result of the mandatory lockdowns. Small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) were particularly hard hit, owing to their small size, limited resources, and cash flow constraints. SMEs in industries including hotels and food services, retail, entertainment, and manufacturing are vulnerable to such social and economic constraints.

For the tests of significant relationship between the challenges and the sustainable strategies of food delivery service reveal the test of the significant relationship between the challenges and the sustainable strategies of food delivery services. Environment $r(30) .352, p=.05$ is positively correlated with challenges. This means that creating a good work environment in business can minimize the challenges encountered by the food establishments, therefore challenges experienced can influence the creation of a good working environment. Nasar et. al (2021) study explains that with simplified solutions, the digitalization of business models would need to embrace innovation principles. Entrepreneurial solutions delivered via mobile phones or smartphones can act as a digital marketplace for businesses and customers to connect.

Conclusions

In general, the majority of respondents confirmed that their food establishments have sustainable strategies for employment, safety, accessibility of the service, responsiveness, and environment. The responders also agreed that these strategies are essential for food establishments owners and managers in navigating the difficulties presented by online delivery services.

The study emphasized the strong relationships between sustainable food delivery service strategies and demographic profiles. In particular, the length of time a business has been in existence seems to affect employment status, and gender and educational background are important factors in determining customer interactions strategies. Among business owners with more education, in particular, technological advancement was noted as being crucial to improving operational efficiency and creating a healthy work atmosphere.

It's interesting to note that there was no significant relationship between the respondents' demographic profiles and the challenges encountered by the food establishments. This implies that the performance and adaptability of food establishments in using food delivery services remained robust and flexible in spite of these factors.

The study validates a significant correlation between the implementation of sustainable practices and the challenges encountered in food delivery services. Creating a positive work atmosphere becomes essential to getting beyond operational obstacles. Moreover, the adoption of advanced technologies such as online platforms and applications not only fosters innovation but also streamlines service delivery, ultimately contributing to enhanced customer satisfaction and operational efficiency in food service establishments.

Recommendations

In light of the findings and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

I. On sustainable strategies of food delivery services to respondents' profile.

Employment status, safety, responsiveness, and environment are connected with the respondent's profile. While the number of years in business operation can influence either an increase or decrease in the employment status. Thus, it is recommended that business owners gain more experience in customer service, employee awareness, and owning a business by attending more training and seminars.

While gender and educational status can influence how business establishments implement business operations, specifically in establishing a good relationship with the customers and being responsive. It is recommended that business owners improve their

skills, knowledge, and attitudes and have constant training and updates on the latest technology that has brought changes in the ways of living of the people/customers.

Lastly, educational status and type of food establishment can influence the environment. It is recommended that business owners have deeper educational knowledge of the business and know how to create a good environment for the customer.

II. On challenges in the food delivery services to respondents' profile.

Challenges in the food delivery services are not related to the respondents' profile. It means the profile of the respondents has nothing to do with the challenges experienced by the business owners. Hence, it is recommended that food delivery operators pay particular attention to encouraging food delivery drivers to improve their delivery quality standards. Delivery drivers must encourage consumers to grade their service experience and write feedback about food delivery services to manage customer expectations.

III. On challenges and the sustainable strategies of food delivery services.

Challenges in the food delivery services are related to the sustainable strategies of food delivery services, specifically the environment, financial structure, and operating pressure. It means that challenges can influence the environment of the food establishment, their business financial status, and how they can continue to operate. Thus, it is recommended that food delivery service providers recognize and emphasize the significant contribution of delivery drivers to the industry's long-term sustainability. Delivery drivers can contribute to creating an environmentally friendly atmosphere through food delivery, improving the financial status of the food establishment, and helping food establishments continue to operate.

Compliance With Ethical Standards

Ethical standards are the morals that align people in doing the right thing. In this paper, ethical standard was applied in the gathering and retrieval of data strictly observing republic act 10173 otherwise known as the data privacy act of 2012.

The participants of this research were fully aware of the purpose of the study and voluntarily answered the questionnaire. They were well informed that the undertaking was handled with strict confidentiality, for it was enclosed in the questionnaire and was legally binding. After the data, all questionnaires were kept by the researcher for burning and or shedding after 5 years. This is the incompliance with the data privacy law.

Acknowledgments

The author acknowledges the assistance of Dr. Ryan O. Tayco to finish this study.

REFERENCES

- 8 Ways to Increase Restaurant Revenue with Outdoor Dining.
<https://www.qsrmagazine.com/growth/fast-casual/8-ways-increase-restaurant-revenue-outdoor-dining/>
- Asinas, J. D., Axalan, L. M. O., Juanites, V. J., Magnaye, L. R. N., Manalo, J. M., Solo, C. A., & Apritado, J. M. M. (2019). Career Advancement of Women in the Hospitality Industry. *Journal of Tourism and Hospitality Research*, 16(1).
- Azoulay, P., Jones, B. F., Kim, J. D., & Miranda, J. (2020). Age and high-growth entrepreneurship. *American Economic Review: Insights*, 2(1), 65-82.
- Burhan, M., Salam, M. T., Abou Hamdan, O., & Tariq, H. (2021). Crisis management in the hospitality sector SMEs in Pakistan during COVID-19. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 98, 103037.
- Chai, L. T., & Yat, D. N. C. (2019). Online food delivery services: making food delivery the new normal. *Journal of Marketing Advances and Practices*, 1(1), 62-77.
- Chaturvedi, R., & Karri, A. (2022). Entrepreneurship in the times of pandemic: Barriers and strategies. *FIIB Business Review*, 11(1), 52-66.
- Fu, H., Okumus, F., Wu, K., & Köseoglu, M. A. (2019). The entrepreneurship research in hospitality and tourism. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 78, 1-12.
- Hong, C., Choi, H. H., Choi, E. K. C., & Joung, H. W. D. (2021). Factors affecting customer intention to use online food delivery services before and during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management*, 48, 509-518.
- Ishak, F. A. C., Zainun, N. A., Karim, M. S., Ungku, Z. A. U. F., & Mohamad, S. F. (2020). The Multifaceted of Themed Restaurant: Exploring the Unique and Vulnerable Elements in Staging Authentic Dining Experience. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 10(3).
- Kapoor, A. P., & Vij, M. (2018). Technology at the dinner table: Ordering food online through mobile apps. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 43, 342-351.
- Li, C., Miroso, M., & Bremer P. (2020). Review of Online Food Delivery Platforms and their Impacts on Sustainability. Sustainability. Dunedin, New Zealand. <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/12/14/5528/htm>
- Muangmee, C., Kot, S., Meekaewkunchorn, N., Kassakorn, N., & Khalid, B. (2021). Factors determining the behavioral intention of using food delivery apps during COVID-19 pandemics. *Journal of theoretical and applied electronic commerce research*, 16(5), 1297-1310.
- Nasar, A., Akram, M., Safdar, M. R., & Akbar, M. S. (2021). A qualitative assessment of

- entrepreneurship amidst COVID-19 pandemic in Pakistan. *Asia Pacific Management Review*.
- Omri, A., & Afi, H. (2020). How can entrepreneurship and educational capital lead to environmental sustainability?. *Structural Change and Economic Dynamics*, 54, 1-10.
- Online Food Delivery – Philippines.
<https://www.statista.com/outlook/emo/online-food-delivery/philippines>
- Prasetyo, Y. T et al (2021). Factors affecting customer satisfaction and loyalty in online food delivery service during the covid-19 pandemic: Its relation with open innovation. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 7(1), 76.
- See-Kwong, G., Soo-Ryue, N., Shiun-Yi, W. & Lily, C. (2017). Outsourcing to online food delivery services: Perspective of F&B business owners. *The Journal of Internet Banking and Commerce*, 22(2), 1-18
- Somashekhar, S. P., Shivaram, H. V., Abhaham, S. J., Dalvi, A., Kumar, A., Gode, D., ... & Pillarisetti, R. R. (2020). ASI's consensus guidelines: ABCs of what to do and what not during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Indian Journal of Surgery*, 82, 240-250.
- Sustainability in Food Delivery Industry.
<https://interbrandpackaging.com/en/2021/06/29/sustainability-in-food-delivery-industry/>
- Tayco, R. O., Tubog, M. V., Rizada, M. L. P., Antique, C. T., Zamora, G. Y., & Espinosa, L. B. (2023). The Effects of the COVID-19 Pandemic on the Tourism Industry in Negros Oriental, Philippines. *Journal of Business on Hospitality and Tourism*, 9(2), 155-187.
- Uike, D. D., & Gupta, M. G. M. (2020). Impact Of Community Support on The Growth Of Female Entrepreneurs During Covid-19 Situation". *PalArch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology*, 17(6), 13492-13505.
- Yeo, V. C. S., Goh, S. K., & Rezaei, S. (2017). Consumer experiences, attitude and behavioral intention toward online food delivery (OFD) services. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer services*, 35, 150-162.
- Zhao, Y & Bacao, F. (2020). What factors determine customers' continuingly using of food delivery apps during the 2019 novel coronavirus pandemic period?. *NCBI Resources*.
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7480677/#:~:text=The%20statistical%20results%20and%20discussions,the%20COVID%2D19%20pandemic%20period>
-